

Body temperature of homeothermic animals – why 36° C?[†]

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Manuscript received 25 October 2002

The question, why body temperature of homeothermic animals during non-hibernation period is around 36°C has been addressed to. Solubility of oxygen in blood has been determined at different temperatures and has been found to be maximum at 37°C. This observation has been shown to be consistent with John Paul's conclusion derived from the minimum noticed by him in the specific heat of water around 36°C.

Majority of homeothermic animals maintain their body temperature during non-hibernation within a few degrees of 36°C. Explanations advanced for this, mostly center around the temperature dependent changes in the rate constants in the enzyme mediated chemical reactions. Paul¹ posed the question, "why 36°C, why not 25 or 48°C or any other. Is it possible that the enzyme systems of the cells evolved as a result of being encouraged to work at 36°C rather than the reverse?" He suggested that the reason for the occurrence of 36°C as body temperature of warm-blooded organisms probably lies in the specific heat of water. He plotted the specific heat of water from Kay and Laby's tables² against temperature and discovered a minimum around 36°C. From this observation he concluded that an organism functioning at this temperature will find it necessary to generate or dissipate minimum amount of heat energy to maintain its temperature constant. In other, words the energy economy of the organism at this temperature is most efficient.

Since the body temperature of 36°C is a consequence of evolution of the organism one should look for optimization of other key operations necessary for the maintenance of life at this temperature. The primary process in the whole cascade of process involved in the maintenance of life is the oxidation using oxygen in the mitochondria. The electrons generated travel to the other side of the membrane through the electron transport chain causing the hydrolysis of ATP leading to the liberation of energy required for metabolic process. It is, therefore, logical to guess that the solubility of oxygen in blood should be maximum in the neighborhood of 36°C.

In view of this we experimentally determined the solubility of oxygen in blood at different temperatures; we experimented with chicken blood. The data plotted in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Solubility of Oxygen in blood at different temperatures.

show a maximum at 37°C. It is also noteworthy that the temperature for the maximum activity of ATPase enzyme is also in the neighborhood of 36°C³. Thus 36°C as body temperature is a consequence of overall optimization of essential metabolic activity of the living organism.

The finding that oxygen solubility in blood is maximum at 37°C is in apparent contrast with the trend in the data on solubility of oxygen in water, which falls steadily with increase in temperature⁴. However, the presence of hemoglobin, which is well known as carrier of oxygen⁵, may be responsible for the increased solubility of oxygen in blood

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

and also the present trend.

The solubility of oxygen in blood at different temperatures was measured using Hansatech oxygen electrode⁶. Blood samples were saturated with oxygen at different temperatures and left for 10 min to equilibrate at that temperature. The oxygen saturated blood samples were then transferred to the cell of the Hansatech oxygen electrode system set at the fixed temperature. The potential difference generated due to the diffusion of oxygen through the membrane was measured and was converted into the concentration of oxygen using the calibration curve constructed by measuring the concentration of oxygen in the aqueous samples saturated at different temperatures. Several repeats were performed to check the reproducibility of the data.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the All India Council of Technical

Education, New Delhi, and to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for supporting this work.

References

1. J. Paul, *Nature*, 1986, **323**, 300.
2. "Kay and Laby's Tables of Physical and Chemical Constants", 14th. ed., Longman, London, 1973, p. 55.
3. D. M. Bollag and S. J. Edelstein, "Protein Method", Wiley-Liss, New York, 1966, p. 20.
4. "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Company, Cleveland, 1957, pp. 1606-1607.
5. A. Katchalsky and P. F. Curran, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Harvard University Press, Cambridge, 1965, p. 203; P. F. Scholander, *Science*, 1960, **131**, 585; E. Hemmingson and P. F. Scholander, *Science*, 1960, **132**, 1379.
6. K. D. Vandergreff and R. I. Shrager, *Methods Enzymol.*, 1944, **232C**, 460.